

AANChOR

All-Atlantic Cooperation for Ocean Research and innovation

Project Information

URL: <https://allatlanticocean.org/>

Project Coordinator: FUNDACAO PARA A CIENCIA E A TECNOLOGIA

Coordinator Country: Portugal

Project duration: 01/10/2018 – 31/03/2023

Funding Programme: H2020-EU.3.2. - SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine, maritime and inland water research, and the bioeconomy

Project Mission

The All-Atlantic Cooperation for Ocean Research and innovation (AANChOR) is a European Union H2020 whose main ambition is to promote the implementation of the South Atlantic Research and Innovation Flagship initiative and the Belém Statement (BS), signed by the European Union (EU), Brazil, and South Africa in 2017, to upscale research and innovation cooperation in the Atlantic Ocean, from Antarctica to the Arctic, started under the Galway Statement.

AANChOR pursues this ambition by providing the Belém Co-Chairs with a framework to identify and contribute to the implementation of concrete long-term collaborative activities, reinforcing international cooperation between Europe, the tropical and South Atlantic countries, connecting with the challenges and research needs of the North Atlantic. By connecting major players in research and innovation from around the Atlantic Ocean, AANChOR aims to build a long-lasting Atlantic Research and Innovation Ocean Community to address grand challenges and opportunities.

Type of synergy with Blue-Cloud

Joint dissemination/communication activities: Blue-Cloud and AANChOR have strongly cooperated together in the dissemination and communication area. The cooperation spanned from the organisation of joint events to promotional activities on social media channels to share the projects' results and reach a broader community.

The projects also co-wrote a joint policy brief "[Nourishing Blue Economy and Sharing Ocean Knowledge - Ocean information for sustainable development](#)" together with the projects EuroSea, AtlantECO, ATLAS, iAtlantic, Nautilus, EUROFLEETS and Odyssea. The policy brief lists recommendations for sustainable ocean observation and management and was developed in the scope of [Horizon Results Booster](#).

The table below presents the events co-organised by Blue-Cloud and AANChOR:

Event title	Date	Event scope
Improving the knowledge of our oceans and seas and bringing them closer to citizens	5 February 2020	Contribute to the implementation of the Galway and the Belém Statements by better understanding the international data/e-infrastructure landscape and the needed federation efforts to accelerate the establishment of a global “Blue-Cloud” able to effectively and efficiently bring data at the service of society
All-Atlantic Ocean Research Forum 2020	6 – 7 February 2020	Forum to showcase the results of cooperation and their impact on the citizens living on the shores of the Atlantic
Towards an All Atlantic Data Space	3 June 2021	Co-organisation of a joint workshop as a side event at the All-Atlantic 2021 . The workshop provided an arena to share the current capability of marine data collection, sharing and services across the Atlantic Ocean, and to debate about EU and international initiatives working to harmonise and facilitate data sharing across the Atlantic, and offered insight into available facilities, tools, training, and the latest open science ‘blue cloud’ technologies to make data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.
Blue-Cloud: An Open Science platform for collaborative marine research across the Atlantic and beyond	14 December 2021	Presentation of the joint policy brief developed in the framework of the EC-funded Horizon Results Booster
South African Webinar & Virtual Workshop	24 May 2022	Participation into the scientific forum to support the dialogue towards sustainable perspectives, priorities and activities connected to the All-Atlantic Declaration